

Kaolinite Oxamyl Interactions

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The adsorptive behaviour of oxamyl with H-, Na- and Ca- kaolinites was studied. The effect of time on adsorption showed that process was diffusion controlled. Kinetic studies showed that reaction was of first order. Maximum adsorption occurred at pH 6.5. The adsorption isotherms and desorption experiments provided evidence for a partly chemisorption and partly physical adsorption of oxamyl on clay surface. Inferences on the protonation of the carbonyl oxygen of the oxamyl molecule by H⁺ ions on kaolinite and/or the coordination of the metallic cations of kaolinite to the carbonyl of amide group found support from adsorption isotherms, thermodynamic parameters, X-ray and IR studies.

NUMEROUS organic chemicals with a wide range of biochemical, chemical and physical properties are being introduced as pesticides and plant growth regulators in modern agriculture. Since these chemicals play a vital role in biochemical and pesticidal processes in plants and soils, it is important that the fate of such chemicals must be thoroughly investigated so that they can be used with utmost advantage and least adverse effects. In this regard interest attaches to the adsorption and complexation of pesticides with clays.

Recently the fate and behaviour of pesticides in soils is a subject of great deal of research¹. Effective pesticidal action of organic chemicals in soil is governed by a number of factors one of which is adsorption on soil colloids. The nature of adsorption affects the ease of pesticidal chemical movement and plant availability, their persistence, degradation and toxicity. So, any investigation on the interaction of pesticidal chemicals with soil or soil constituents besides throwing some light on the fundamental behaviour of organic chemical also will be of great practical importance. While the interaction and adsorption of ionic pesticides on clay surface has been extensively studied², the relatively less work was done on the reaction mechanism of non-ionic pesticides on soil colloids.

Clay minerals constitute the most reactive portion of soil. Clay provides heterogeneous chemical spots in the form of sorbed water around cations³, lattice surface oxygen⁴, electron accepting sites⁵ and transition metals in higher valency states. Thus an organic chemical may be adsorbed on the clay surface by ion exchange, protonation, hydrogen bonding, coordination⁶, ion-dipole interaction, van der Waal's forces, charge transfer complex and hemisalt formation⁷.

Oxamyl {methyl 2-(dimethylamino)-N-[(methylamino) carbonyl]oxy]-2-oxoethanimidothioate}, a

formulation of DuPont de Nemours & Co. Inc., Wilmington, U. S. A. is a recently introduced broad spectrum non-ionic pesticide used as nematocide^{8,9}.

Adsorption isotherms, X-ray, infrared and thermodynamic studies can be used to provide information on the mechanism of interaction of organic pesticides with clays. The main objective of the present investigation was to investigate the mechanism of adsorption and interaction of oxamyl with acid and base saturated kaolinites in dilute clay-water suspensions. It was considered that such a study will be useful in the efficient utilization of chemical (oxamyl) in kaolinitic soils.

Experimental

Kaolinite used in these studies was from Bath, South Carolina, and was a monomineralic standard of Project No. 49 of the American Petroleum Institute. Less than 2 μm clay fraction was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation. The suspension was then converted into chloride free sodium and hydrogen ion saturated kaolinites by Aldrich and Buchanan's method as described elsewhere¹⁰. Calcium saturated kaolinite was prepared from the sodium form, by treating it with CaCl₂. The clays were used for experiments immediately after their preparation. The concentration of all the suspensions varied from 14.0 to 15.7 gl^{-1} . The cation exchange capacity (CEC) as determined by Ganguli's method was 106 μ equiv/g clay.

To study the effect of time experiments were conducted taking 10 ml of appropriate clay-water suspensions in their H-, Na- and Ca-forms in several glass stoppered tubes and were treated with 5 and 15 ml of oxamyl solution (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), the volume was made to 25 ml with distilled water. The samples were kept in contact for 3, 6, 9, 15, 18, 24, 27, 30, 33, 48, 54 and 72 hr with continuous shaking in a

mechanical shaker. The mixtures were then centrifuged and the oxamyl in the supernatants was estimated spectrophotometrically at 435 nm¹². The amount of oxamyl adsorbed at various intervals of time was obtained than the amount of oxamyl added minus remaining in the supernatants.

To study the pH effect adsorption experiments were conducted at pH values adjusted to 2, 4, 6, 6.5, 7, 8, 10 and 12 by 0.01M HCl or 0.01M NaOH as required. For pH study, 10 ml of H-, Na- and Ca- saturated kaolinite suspensions and 5 and 15 ml of oxamyl solutions (1000 µg/ml) were taken in glass stoppered tubes and the tubes were shaken for 33 hr in a mechanical shaker. The samples were then centrifuged and oxamyl adsorbed and remaining in the supernatant was estimated and calculated as above.

Adsorption experiments were conducted by taking 10 ml of the appropriate kaolinite suspensions in H-, Na- and Ca-forms, in a large number of glass stoppered tubes, adding various amounts (0 to 15 ml) of standard oxamyl solution (1000 µg/ml), making up the volume to 25 ml with distilled water and shaking for 30 hr at 20 and 50°. Oxamyl in the centrifuged supernatants was estimated as described above. Adsorption isotherms were plotted between the equilibrium concentration (mM) of oxamyl in the suspensions and amount of oxamyl adsorbed (µ mole/g clay) (Fig. 3).

In the desorption experiments 10 ml of oxamyl complexed kaolinites were treated with water, 1 ml of 0.1M KCl and 0.1M BaCl₂ respectively, the volume adjusted to 25 ml with water and the samples were shaken for 33 hr, then oxamyl estimated as above. The results are shown in Table 2.

The results of adsorption were correlated with X-ray and IR studies. For X-ray analysis less than 2 µm acid and base saturated suspensions of kaolinite and their complexes with oxamyl were allowed to dry on microglass slides to form well oriented flat layers. X-ray diffractions were recorded on a General Electric Diffraction unit at a speed of 0.4 degree 2θ per minute using filtered CuK_α radiation. For IR analysis thin self supporting films of the sample were prepared by drying the kaolinite water suspension (H-, Na- and Ca- forms) and their complexed clay-water suspension at room temperature on polythene sheets. The spectra of the samples and oxamyl (pure) were recorded in the range 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. on a Beckman IR-20 double beam spectrophotometer.

All experiments were done in duplicate with suitable reagent and clay blanks.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption of oxamyl as a function of time on H-, Na- and Ca- saturated kaolinites for two

Fig. 1. Effect of time on the adsorption of oxamyl by kaolinites (o) hydrogen form (●) sodium form, (x) calcium form. Oxamyl added per g of clay. 1(a) 146 µ mole 1(b) 438 µ mole, 2(a) 169 µ mole, 2(b) 480 µ mole, 3(a) 150 µ mole and 3(b) 449 µ mole.

concentrations of oxamyl is shown in Fig. 1. The adsorption of oxamyl was found to be increased with time upto an interval of 33 hr after which it became constant. Such a slow rate of attaining the equilibrium indicates that process is at least partly of chemical nature¹³. On applying the simple kinetic rate laws, the calculation of the rate constants at different time intervals and concentrations gave values as given in Table 1, which indicated

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TIME ON THE ADSORPTION OF OXAMYL, WITH H-, Na- AND Ca- SATURATED KAOLINITES AT 20°C

Form of Clay	µ moles of oxamyl added per g clay	Rate constant $k \times 10^6 (\text{sec}^{-1})$	Half life period ($t_{1/2}$) of adsorption in hr
H-kaolinite	163	2.27	84.9
	489	2.20	87.5
Na-kaolinite	146	2.35	81.9
	438	2.30	83.7
Ca-kaolinite	152	2.20	87.5
	456	2.08	92.4

TABLE 2—DESORPTION OF OXAMYL, BY DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES FROM THE H-, Na- AND Ca- SATURATED KAOLINITE—OXAMYL COMPLEXES

Form of Clay	Oxamyl adsorbed µ mole/g clay	Oxamyl desorbed (µ mole/g clay) by		
		H ₂ O	KCl	BaCl ₂
H-kaolinite	134	33	62	62
Na-kaolinite	138	47	86	83
Ca-kaolinite	125	37	81	84

that the adsorption reaction was of first order and the half time of adsorption ($t_{1/2}$ values) increased

with increasing oxamyl concentration, suggesting a diffusion controlled process¹⁴.

The effect of *pH* on the adsorption of oxamyl on kaolinites is given in Fig. 2. Both at higher and lower concentration of oxamyl added, adsorption increased with *pH* up to a value of *pH* 6.5 and beyond this value the adsorption has a tendency to decrease. The *pK* value of oxamyl in distilled water as determined by the conductivity method was 6.2. Its potentiometric titration with 0.001*M* HCl and 0.001*M* NaOH showed that oxamyl behaves as an ampholyte with *pK*₁ value 4 and *pK*₂ 8 (Fig. 4). As expected, the maximum adsorption

Fig. 2. Effect of *pH* on the adsorption of oxamyl by kaolinites, (o) hydrogen form, (●) sodium form, (x) calcium form. Oxamyl added per g of clay. 1(a) 146 μ mole, 1(b) 438 μ mole, 2(a) 160 μ mole, 2(b) 480 μ mole, 3(a) 150 μ mole and 3(b) 449 μ mole.

occurs in the vicinity of *pK* value (6.2). It appears that at *pH* values lower than 6.5 oxamyl and at *pH* values greater than 6.5. Na⁺ oxamyl are formed by interaction with H⁺ (from HCl) and Na⁺ (from NaOH) ions. These ion complexes are not adsorbable on acid and base saturated kaolinites. This is supported by desorption studies. In the absence of competition from H⁺ or Na⁺ ions at *pH* 6.5 a direct association of the pesticide with the cations on the clay surface probably occurs giving maximum adsorption^{15,16}.

The empirical Freundlich relationship is used to describe the oxamyl adsorption results on kaolinite. The linear form of the equation is :

$$X/m = KC^{1/n} \text{ or } \ln X/m = \ln K + 1/n \ln C$$

where *X/m* = oxamyl adsorbed (μ g/g clay), *C* = equilibrium concentration in solution (μ g/ml), *K* and *1/n* are constants which characterize the adsorption

capacity for the oxamyl. A plot of $\ln X/m$ against $\ln C$ gave linear curves in all the cases at both the temperatures (Fig. 5). *K* is the amount adsorbed for a unit equilibrium concentration of oxamyl and *1/n* the slope is a measure of the intensity of adsorption reflecting the degrees to which adsorption is a function of concentration. The values are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FREUNDLICH CONSTANTS FOR ADSORPTION OF OXAMYL ON H-, Na- and Ca-KAOLINITES AT 20 AND 50°

Nature of Clay	Temp. (K)	Freundlich Constants	
		K	1/n
H-kaol.	293	1089 ± 2.0	0.545 ± 0.005
	323	1072 ± 1.8	0.500 ± 0.002
Na-kaol.	293	1144 ± 2.6	0.565 ± 0.004
	323	1134 ± 1.9	0.530 ± 0.005
Ca-kaol.	293	1036 ± 3.1	0.525 ± 0.002
	323	1002 ± 0.8	0.490 ± 0.003

± Standard error of estimate.

An examination of Table 3 indicated that the values of the sorption intensity, *1/n* were always of less unity. These were indicative of a significant non-linearity in the isotherms (L type isotherm) and an exponential decrease in the sorption energy as the proportion of adsorption sites saturated with oxamyl became larger¹⁷. The non-linearity varied with the type of cation of kaolinite and the temperature. These factors also influenced the adsorption of oxamyl. This found further confirmation from the values of *K*, Freundlich constant. The higher values of *K* at 20° than at 50° in all cases pointed to a decrease in the adsorption of the pesticide with rise in temperature i. e., the interaction of oxamyl with H-, Na- and Ca-kaolinites was of an exothermic nature and followed the order Na-kaol > H-kaol > Ca-kaol.

Adsorption of oxamyl on H-, Na- and Ca-saturated kaolinite suspensions (1.40-1.57% w/v) in the equilibrium concentration range 0 to 2.2 mM at 20 and 50° yielded isotherms as shown in Fig. 3. An examination of adsorption isotherms revealed that they were similar to class 'L' as defined by Giles *et al*¹⁸. This kind of isotherm may arise due to minimum competition of solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. The slope of isotherm steadily decreases with rise in solute concentration because vacant sites become less accessible with the progressive covering of the surface. The curvilinear isotherm suggests that the number of available sites for the adsorption become a limiting factor¹⁹. Fig. 3 also showed that a greater amount of oxamyl is adsorbed by the base saturated kaolinites than the acid saturated and followed the order Na-kaol > H-kaol > Ca-kaol. Further an increase in temperature from 20 to 50° decreased the adsorption, which may be due to increased desorption by increasing the thermal energy of adsorbate. The uniformity of

the curves at both the temperatures also showed that the temperature does not change the nature of the reaction but influence the number of adsorption sites and/or affinity for oxamyl.

The results of desorption (Table 2) indicate that the part of the oxamyl adsorbed on H-, Na- and Ca-kaolinites can be desorbed by water or solutions of inorganic salts, indicating that the appreciable adsorption of oxamyl on clay surface occurs by ionic interactions and by long range attractive forces.

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherm of oxamyl on H(x), Na(●), Ca(▲) at 30° and on H(○), Na(⊙) and Ca(Δ)-kaolinites at 50°.

Fig. 4. Variation of pH during treatment of oxamyl with acid or alkali.

Above propositions were also supported by thermodynamic parameters. From the adsorption curves (Fig. 3) the thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_o), the standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes were calculated according the Biggar and Cheung method²⁰. The values are recorded in Table 4.

Fig. 5. Freundlich isotherms of oxamyl adsorption on H(x), Na(●), Ca(▲) at 30° and on H(○), Na(⊙) and Ca(Δ) kaolinites at 50°.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXAMYL ADSORPTION ON H-, Na- and Ca-KAOLINITES AT 20 AND 50°

Thermodynamic parameters	H-kaolinite		Na-kaolinite		Ca-kaolinite	
	20	50	20	50	20	50
K_o	2026	863	2234	932	1803	802
ΔG° (K J/mole)	-18.55	-18.16	-18.79	-18.36	-18.27	-17.96
ΔH° (K J/mole)	-22.39		-22.94		-21.25	
ΔS° (J/mole)	-13.10		-14.17		-10.17	

An examination of Table 4 showed that the values of K_o were always higher than unity, i. e., oxamyl had a preference for kaolinite surface. The values confirmed the deductions that adsorption of oxamyl on kaolinites decreased with a rise in temperature and order of adsorption was Na-kaol>H-kaol>Ca-kaol.

The values of ΔG° were negative at both the temperatures and increased with rise in temperature pointing towards the spontaneity of the reaction with a greater affinity of kaolinites for oxamyl. The values of ΔG° showed that for the oxamyl driving forces of reaction, the strength of adsorption and degree of order attained during adsorption reaction is Na->H->Ca- kaolinites.

The enthalpy changes (negative value ΔH°) showed that the reaction is of exothermic nature with a binding of the oxamyl molecules to the acid and base saturated kaolinites and adsorption occurs through bonding mechanism²¹. The values of ΔH° also confirmed our earlier inferences on the affinity of oxamyl. The negative value of ΔS° indicated that there is no configurational changes and the complexes of oxamyl with kaolinites are stable²².

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